

Efficacy of Partially Absorbable versus Non-Absorbable Mesh in Laparoscopic Inguinal Hernia Repair: A Comparative Study

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Abstract:

Introduction: The selection of mesh material is a critical factor influencing patient outcomes in hernia repair, potentially outweighing the impact of the surgical technique employed. Research has compared polypropylene mesh with modified composite mesh (a combination of polypropylene and polyglactin), showing that composite mesh results in fewer foreign body reactions, reduced post-operative complications, and improved long-term quality of life. This study aimed to evaluate and compare the early outcomes of non-absorbable polypropylene mesh versus partially absorbable composite mesh in laparoscopic inguinal hernia repair.

Methods: The study included 78 patients with elective reducible indirect inguinal hernias. The participants were divided into two groups of 39 each: Group A, which received partially absorbable composite lightweight meshes, and Group B, which received non-absorbable polypropylene meshes. All patients underwent laparoscopic inguinal hernia repair using the transabdominal preperitoneal (TAPP) approach. Post-operative comparisons between the groups were made based on parameters such as age distribution, inguinodynia, analgesia requirements, foreign body sensation, presence of lumps (hematoma or seroma), and return to work activities, and recurrence rates.

Results: The average age of the patients was 51.14 ± 12.91 years, with the majority falling in the 51–60 years age group. Initially, no significant difference in transient neuralgia was observed between the two groups. However, at six weeks post-operation, Group A reported significantly less pain. Foreign body sensation was notably higher in Group B, though this difference was not significant over time.

Conclusion: The findings suggest that composite mesh may be preferable for laparoscopic inguinal hernia repair, as it is associated with reduced pain, less foreign body sensation, and a quicker return to work compared to polypropylene mesh.

Keywords: Inguinal Hernia, Mesh Repair; Non-Absorbable; Partially Absorbable.

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Introduction

Abdominal wall hernias are prevalent, with an overall incidence of 1.7%, rising to 4% in individuals over 45 years of age. Inguinal hernias constitute 75% of abdominal hernias, with a lifetime risk of 27% in men and 3% in women. Hernias involve an abnormal protrusion of abdominal contents through a normal or abnormal body cavity opening, occurring in 5–7% of the population. Among these, inguinal hernias are the most common. Inguinal hernias are categorized into two types: indirect and direct. An indirect inguinal hernia occurs when the contents protrude

through the internal inguinal ring, while a direct inguinal hernia protrudes through Hesselbach's triangle in the posterior wall of the inguinal canal. The open repair techniques for inguinal hernias, aimed at reinforcing the posterior wall, have evolved over the past century, including Bassini, McVay, and Shouldice repairs. Recently, there has been a shift towards tension-free repairs using prosthetic mesh, both in open and laparoscopic procedures [1-3]. The first laparoscopic hernia repair technique, introduced by Ger in 1982, involved closing the defect by transabdominal

fixation of the peritoneal sac to adjacent tissues using Michel staples [4]. Currently, laparoscopic pre-peritoneal mesh hernioplasty is becoming increasingly popular. The use of prosthetic meshes is crucial for hernia repair as it reconstructs the groin area by mimicking traditional pre-peritoneal repairs. Mesh usage has been associated with a 30–50% reduction in recurrence rates. Various biomaterials are used for hernia meshes, each with distinct advantages and disadvantages. Polypropylene, the most commonly used biomaterial, is non-absorbable, provides a tensile strength of approximately 320 N/cm [4-6], and is densely woven, which can lead to an intense inflammatory response and reduced elasticity of the abdominal wall. Partially absorbable composite meshes, which include materials like polyglactin and polyglecaprone, offer lower pain and fibrosis and provide a strength of around 100-130 N/cm [6]. Despite advancements in hernia repair, recurrences remain a challenge, and the search for an ideal mesh that minimizes recurrence continues [7]. The overall recurrence rate varies from 1.7% to 10%, depending on the type of repair used [8,9]. An ideal mesh should be chemically inert, non-inflammatory, non-malignant, non-allergenic, moldable, inexpensive, readily available, and non-immunogenic [4]. Research suggests that the choice of mesh is a more critical determinant of patient outcomes than the repair technique itself [10].

Comparative studies of polypropylene and modified composite meshes (polypropylene and polyglactin) have indicated that composite meshes are associated with fewer foreign body reactions, reduced postoperative complications, and improved long-term quality of life [11]. However, there is limited research on early outcomes, such as seroma or hematoma formation, inguinodynia, foreign body sensation, testicular issues, and return to normal activity. The present study aims to evaluate the differences between non-absorbable polypropylene and partially absorbable composite meshes in the context of transabdominal pre-peritoneal (TAPP) repair of inguinal hernias.

Material and Methods

This prospective study comprised 78 patients with elective reducible indirect inguinal hernias. Inclusion criteria included patients aged 18 years or older with unilateral, primary, reducible inguinal hernias, and no contraindications for TAPP mesh

hernioplasty. Exclusion criteria encompassed patients older than 72 years, those with a thin external aponeurosis, concurrent surgical pathologies requiring simultaneous operations, bilateral inguinal hernias, strangulated inguinal hernias, collagen or connective tissue disorders, immunocompromised individuals, pregnant women, and those with morbid obesity. The study cohort was divided into two groups of 39 patients each: Group A and Group B. All patients underwent laparoscopic inguinal hernia repair using the TAPP approach, performed by experienced surgeons. Group A received partially absorbable composite lightweight meshes, while Group B was implanted with non-absorbable polypropylene meshes. Random assignment determined the mesh type for each patient. General anesthesia was administered, and patients were catheterized with a scrotal wrap applied to prevent pneumoscrotum. No other interventions, aside from mesh implantation, were performed during the procedure.

Post-operatively, patients received appropriate care and were advised to avoid heavy lifting, prolonged coughing, and straining. They were discharged on the second day if no complications were observed. The duration of hospital stay and any post-operative complications were recorded. At discharge, patients were instructed to use analgesics (NSAIDs or opioids if needed) and to refrain from strenuous activities for the first week.

Follow-up evaluations occurred at 6 weeks and 3 months post-surgery in the outpatient department. The comparison between the two groups was based on the following parameters: age distribution, inguinodynia or pain using the visual analog scale (VAS), analgesic requirements, foreign body sensation, presence of a lump (hematoma or seroma), return to work activities, and recurrence.

Results

In this study, the age distribution of the participants reveals a diverse cohort with a predominance in the middle-aged group. As shown in Table 1, the majority of participants (32.05%) were between 51 and 60 years old, followed by those aged 41 to 50 years, constituting 20.51% of the sample.

The age groups 31 to 40 years and 61 to 70 years each comprised 17.95% of the participants. A small fraction of the cohort, just 1.28%, was aged between 71 and 80 years (Table 1).

Table 1: Age distribution of study participants

Age Group (Years)	n	%
21–30	8	10.26
31–40	14	17.95
41–50	16	20.51
51–60	25	32.05

61–70	14	17.95
71–80	1	1.28
Total	78	100
Mean	51.14 ± 12.91	

Tables 2,3 and 4 show parameters measured in study participants at 0, 6 and 12 weeks, respectively. Inguinodynia was assessed using the VAS scoring system, with mean scores recorded for both groups at 0 weeks, 6 weeks, and 12 weeks.

The Mann-Whitney test showed no significant difference in scores at 0 weeks ($P = 0.075$). However, at both 6 weeks and 12 weeks, the composite mesh group exhibited significantly lower VAS scores compared to the non-absorbable

mesh group ($P < 0.05$). In the early post-operative phase, 6 patients in Group A experienced a foreign body sensation, whereas 21 patients in Group B reported the same (Table 2). The Chi-square test indicated a statistically significant difference with a p-value of less than 0.05.

Over time, the number of patients in both groups reporting this sensation decreased. However, the difference between the groups remained significant according to the Chi-square analysis.

Table 2: Baseline parameters (0 week) in study participants

Parameter	Non-absorbable Mesh (Group B)	Partially-absorbable Mesh (Group A)	P Value
VAS	7.48	8.28	0.25
Testicular VAS	0.53	0.42	0.45
Analgesic	29	31	0.32
Lump	5	2	0.10
FBS	21	6	<0.05

Table 3: Parameters at 6 weeks post-operative follow-up

Parameter	Non-absorbable Mesh (Group B)	Partially-absorbable Mesh (Group A)	P Value
VAS	5.43	4.18	<0.05
Testicular VAS	0.34	0.31	0.72
Analgesic	1	1	-
Lump	2	2	-
FBS	14	3	<0.05

Table 4: Parameters at 12 weeks post-operative follow-up

Parameter	Non-absorbable Mesh (Group B)	Partially-absorbable Mesh (Group A)	P Value
VAS	2.47	3.33	<0.05
Testicular VAS	0.01	0.01	-
Analgesic	10	6	<0.05
Lump	1	0	0.23
FBS	5	1	<0.05

Patients from both groups were discharged on day 2.1 ± 0.6 days, provided no complications were noted. They were then asked about their return to work. On average, patients in Group A resumed their occupations after 12 days (12.04 ± 2.32), whereas those in Group B returned 2 days later, at 14 days (14.18 ± 1.95). The difference between the groups was statistically significant, as determined by the independent Student's t-test.

Discussion

Few studies have examined the short-term (3 months) comparison between composite meshes and non-absorbable meshes in laparoscopic hernia repair. Our study, involving a straightforward design, included 78 patients who underwent TAPP repair for inguinal hernia. The average age of participants was 51.14 ± 12.91 years, consistent with findings from Shah et al. [7] and Bangash et

al. [12]. Most patients were in the 51–60 year age group. The increasing incidence of hernias with age, as observed in our study, is corroborated by Ruhl and Everhart [13] and Abramson et al. [14]. These results align with those reported by Schopf et al. [15]. Post-operatively, pain was assessed using a Visual Analog Scale (VAS) at 0, 6, and 12 weeks. The student t-test indicated no significant difference in pain scores between the two groups immediately after surgery, consistent with other studies. However, after 6 weeks, Group A experienced significantly less pain, and this trend continued through 12 weeks. This finding is in line with the study by Smietanski et al. [16]. Compared to sutured repairs, mesh repairs resulted in less postoperative pain. Despite this, mesh repairs have been associated with increased reports of postoperative pain and discomfort. Small-pore size meshes can lead to granuloma bridging due to

foreign body reactions, forming a stiff scar plate that reduces flexibility. However, Bringman et al. reported conflicting results [17,18]. Foreign body sensations were more commonly reported in Group B (83%), aligning with findings from Bringman et al. [19], Horstmann et al. [20], Paajanen [21], and Kalra et al. [22]. These studies found that polypropylene mesh led to more frequent foreign body sensations compared to composite mesh. By 12 weeks, the significance of this sensation decreased, with less than 70% of patients reporting no foreign body sensation, though 20% in Group A and 36% in Group B still experienced it.

No significant difference was observed between the groups regarding the presence of lumps. This is consistent with the results of Bangash et al. and Schumpelick et al. Composite meshes, being more elastic and microporous than non-absorbable meshes, tend to form a more flexible scar in the inguinal canal [12,23]. This may explain the lower incidence of seroma formation and surgical site infections in patients with composite mesh compared to non-absorbable mesh.

Group A also demonstrated an earlier return to work activities, which, although statistically significant, was numerically minimal. This may account for the reduced postoperative pain associated with composite meshes. This finding aligns with studies by Post et al., Chowbey et al., Heikkinen et al., Langenbach et al., and the meta-analysis by Sajid et al. [2,24-28]. Regarding recurrence, only 1 patient in Group B experienced a recurrence. However, our study's limitation is its small sample size and short duration, in contrast to other studies with larger sample sizes and longer follow-up periods of 6 months to a year or more.

Conclusion

This study compared non-absorbable and composite meshes for laparoscopic inguinal hernia repair, finding significant differences in VAS pain scores at 6 and 12 weeks post-operatively. Early return to work and lower recurrence rates with composite mesh were statistically significant, with no surgical site infections in either group. Composite mesh is thus recommended for its lower pain, reduced foreign body sensation, and faster recovery.

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